

USING GAZE-TRACKING TO ASSESS COGNITIVE LOAD IN LOWER LIMB PROSTHETIC USERS

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INTRODUCTION

Clinical assessments of lower limb prosthetic users primarily focus on performance and psychological outcome measures [1]. The assessment of cognitive load, however, is often neglected.

It is known that lower limb prosthetic users have to deal with an increase in cognitive load (e.g., by focusing on the device during walking) [2,3], and research has shown that their gaze behavior, which indicates the focus of attention [4], indeed differs from the able-bodied population [5].

Therefore, gaze tracking might be an instrument to measure cognitive load while using a lower limb prosthesis, but this has not been investigated before. The aim of the present study was to test the feasibility of using gaze tracking for the assessment of cognitive load in lower limb prosthesis users.

METHODS

Two participants (P01 and P02) with unilateral transfemoral amputation (mobility level K3) participated in this pilot study. During the study, the participants wore a microprocessor-controlled prosthetic knee joint (GeniumX3, Ottobock). The participants were asked to perform a battery of tasks, including level walking (LW), walking on uneven ground (UW), obstacle avoidance (OB), a combination of stair ascent and ramp descent (SURD), as well as ramp ascent and stair descent (RUSD), in addition to a task outside of the laboratory (staircase climbing, SCUp/SCDown). For each task, the participants were asked to focus their visual attention on a target at the end of the walkway, unless they felt the need to look somewhere else (i.e., down on the pathway).

A mobile eye tracker (Tobii Pro Glasses 3) measured gaze location (i.e., focus of attention) during all tasks, and target fixation time expressed in % relative to total trial time was calculated. In addition, the participants were asked to rate the perceived cognitive demand of each task on an interval scale from 1 (very, very low) to 9 (very, very high).

Kinematic data were recorded from all laboratory-based tasks using an optical motion capture system.

Spearman's rank correlation coefficients were determined to describe the relationship between gaze data and perceived cognitive load.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 1 shows a significant negative correlation between target fixation time and subjective rating of

cognitive load for P01 ($r = -0.91$, $p < 0.01$). Contrarily, P02 perceived all tasks as very easy (rated as 1) and the target fixation times did not decrease substantially (no correlation coefficients could be determined).

The results of P01 highlight the potential of a mobile eye tracker to measure cognitive load representative of perception.

Furthermore, the target fixation time was able to show that the tasks were not difficult enough for P02 to have an effect on cognitive load, leading to inconclusive results in this case (Figure 1).

Figure 1 Target fixation times (in %, mean \pm standard deviation) and perception of cognitive load (red dashed lines and asterisks) of all tasks for P01 and P02.

CONCLUSIONS

This pilot study has shown that using a mobile eye tracker could be an easy, objective measure for assessing the cognitive load of lower limb prosthetic users. Importantly, the approach of measuring cognitive load with a mobile eye tracker could be used outside of a laboratory environment, in the everyday lives of the users.

Future analyses of the kinematic data including more participants will be conducted to investigate if and how an increase in cognitive load affects performance.

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